

VeriFish

The sustainability indicator framework to communicate responsible aquafood production and consumption patterns

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FIP	Fisheries Improvement Project
GRSF	Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries
GSSI	Global Sustainable SeaFood Initiative
NGO	Non Governmental Organisation
PEFCR	Product Environmental Footprint Category Rule
SB	Steering Board
STECF	Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries

Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary	5
2. Introduction	6
2.1. Background and Rationale	6
2.2. Objectives of the Deliverable	8
3. Indicators identification and selection	9
3.1. Attributes: Capture fisheries	9
3.2. Attributes: Aquaculture	11
3.3. Attributes: Nutrition and health	14
3.4. Indicators: Capture fisheries	16
3.5. Indicators: Aquaculture	28
3.6. Indicators: Nutrition and health	35
3.7. Social and economic indicators	42
3.8. Indicators for sustainability of aquafood products	44
3.9. Sources of data: Capture Fisheries	45
3.10 Sources of data: Aquaculture	46
3.11 Sources of data: Nutrients	47
4. Indicator Quality	49
5. VeriFish Framework	51
6. Conclusions	53
6.1. Summary of Findings	53
6.2. Implications for Future Work	53
6.3. Recommendations for stakeholders	54

Table of Tables

Table 1: Aquaculture production system classification and origin ⁷	13
Table 2a: Capture fisheries proposed indicators - Environment	25
Table 2b: Capture fisheries proposed indicators - Management	27
Table 3a: Aquaculture proposed indicators - Environment	32
Table 3b: Aquaculture proposed indicators - Management	34
Table 4. Summary of indicator selection for high-quality protein in aquafood	38
Table 5. Summary of nutrition indicators for aquafood	40

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable defines a comprehensive suite of indicators designed to assess and communicate sustainability in the aquafood sector, specifically focusing on capture fisheries, aquaculture, and nutrition. These indicators address critical dimensions of sustainability, environmental, and nutritional impacts, providing a measurable and evidence-based foundation for evaluating sustainability.

Fisheries indicators: A suite of 21 indicators has been identified to measure sustainability in capture fisheries. These indicators include stock status metrics such as B_{MSY} (biomass at maximum sustainable yield) and F_{MSY} (fishing mortality at maximum sustainable yield), which assess whether fish populations are harvested within ecological limits. Indicators for ecosystem impacts evaluate habitat disruption, trophic effects, and bycatch rates, with a particular focus on vulnerable or endangered species. Climate-related indicators, such as CO₂ emissions per kilogram of landed catch, highlight the carbon footprint of fishing activities and the environmental impact of gear types. Additional metrics address governance, such as compliance with fisheries management plans and efforts to prevent illegal, unreported, and unregulated fishing. These indicators are critical for monitoring the health of fish stocks, minimising ecological harm, and ensuring long-term viability of marine resources.

Aquaculture indicators span a range of environmental, economic, and operational aspects, reflecting the complexity of this sector, as well as provide insights into the sustainability of aquaculture practices. Key metrics include feed efficiency, such as the food conversion ratio, and the use of wild-caught marine ingredients in feeds, which have implications for marine food webs. Indicators for waste and pollution, such as nutrient emissions and plastic reuse or recycling, assess the environmental footprint of aquaculture facilities. Habitat impact metrics evaluate site selection and potential alterations to surrounding ecosystems. Biosecurity measures, including antimicrobial use and disease management practices, reflect efforts to mitigate risks to animal health and productivity.

Nutrition indicators focus on the composition and health benefits of aquafoods. These include high-quality protein content, which is essential for muscle maintenance and overall health, and the presence of omega-3 fatty acids such as EPA and DHA, which support heart and brain health. Micronutrient indicators vitamins and minerals, such as vitamin D, selenium, and iodine, which are vital for immune function, bone health, and metabolic processes. The indicators also consider energy content, sodium, and the ratio of saturated to unsaturated fats, reflecting the overall nutritional profile of aquafood. These metrics align with public health objectives, promoting aquafood as a nutrient-dense, potentially climate-friendly protein source.

The indicators provide a basis for a rigorous framework for evaluating sustainability across fisheries, aquaculture, and nutrition. They are grounded in scientifically validated methodologies and reflect key priorities such as biodiversity conservation, resource efficiency, and public health. By enabling the measurement and communication of sustainability in the aquafood sector, these indicators can support informed decision-making and foster a more sustainable future for this vital sector in Europe.

2. Introduction

VeriFish aims to simplify and standardise communication of aquafood sustainability for re-use in various food chains. More specifically, the project is developing a framework of verifiable indicators, based on reliable data from European and global sources. These indicators are intended to help actors in aquafood chains to provide information (nutrition, environmental, societal) about products, thereby enabling consumers to make informed decisions at purchase. Using white labelled media products and a prototype web application, VeriFish will exemplify how verifiable data can be collated by actors and shared with consumers, ultimately helping to promote more sustainable consumption patterns and responsible aquafood production.

2.1. Background and Rationale

The rationale for the VeriFish indicator framework is centred around the need to simplify and standardise communication about aquafood sustainability, including responsible production, and nudge consumption patterns towards good practices. Currently, there are no harmonised indicators or standardised approaches to inform citizens about sustainability, health benefits, or climate impacts associated with seafood and/ or aquaculture products. The complexity of fisheries and aquaculture food chains makes it difficult for producers and retailers to present information in easily understood formats and, thereby, support consumers in making informed choices, especially regarding sustainability and healthy eating.

2.1.1. Background

Many actors (e.g., governments, companies, and non-governmental organisations [NGOs]) require comprehensive information on performance, sustainability, quality, and food safety to better understand and manage food supply chains. Reports include topics such as exploitation, effects on endangered and threatened species (ETP), climate and ecosystem impacts, and biodiversity, use of resource, child labour, and supply chain transparency. Even the act of reporting can serve as an indicator of sustainability. Such reports enable organisations, large and small, to communicate their performance on environmental risks, unique product attributes, and production practices to target audiences empowering customers—partners, investors, citizens— to make well-informed choices. As sustainability reporting and disclosure have become more widespread, demand for accurate and transparent data has risen. At the same time, the volume of data and tools have rapidly expanded, although the quality of data and tools is not always obvious. With growing numbers of reporting schemes, and complexity regarding the meaning of outcomes, there is an increasing need for FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) and validated data, with transparent collection processes as well as well-defined indicators. However, sustainability communication often struggles with providing timely and verifiable information, which can increase costs for both data providers and consumers over time due to inefficiencies and lack of trust.

VeriFish aims to bridge this gap by helping actors to communicate added value and benefits of products to potential consumers. By developing cost-effective and transparent approaches for communicating scientifically verifiable sustainability and nutritional information, VeriFish will empower actors and consumers alike. Currently, European and global data repositories provide plenty of data to communicate sustainability efforts. The challenge lies in translating these data—such as those used for certifications and improvement trajectories—into a language that is clear, informative, and engaging for citizens, who have specific concerns (e.g., climate change and/or nutrition) and preferences (species, minimal waste), but are underserved by current practices. The VeriFish framework will address this need, providing more effective ways for actors to connect with consumers and deliver precise, reliable, and understandable information. The framework will be incorporated into and promoted by media products and a prototype web application to ensure accessibility and usability, ultimately demonstrating how informed purchasing decisions might be supported and responsible consumption promoted.

2.1.2. Rationale

The rationale for sustainable aquafood production lies in the urgent need to balance human demands for food quantity and quality within the limitations of global natural resources. Achieving this balance is critical to assure aquatic ecosystems for both current and future generations. Unsustainable practices endanger the long-term availability of vital natural resources and, even though many aquatic resources are renewable, they are not infinite. Sustainability, therefore, is about safeguarding the conditions necessary for this ‘renewability’.

All food systems, especially those reliant on natural aquatic ecosystems, must be sustainable and responsibility is shared by both producers and consumers. Indicators must serve as collaborative tools to guide actions and, thus, the rationale for VeriFish sustainability indicators is to foster a system where actors (not just producers) and citizens (not just consumers) can work together towards responsible food consumption.

VeriFish aims to ensure that:

- Consumers can trust nutritional quality of aquafood products
- Impacts on biodiversity and the environment are minimised
- Use of natural resources is responsible so as not to exceed what is sustainable.

From the perspective of aquafood actors, the VeriFish framework must empower them to:

- Promote and market products based on scientifically verifiable indicators for environmental, social and economic, and nutrition and health data

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- Facilitate the transparency needed to verify data underpinning claims and advertisements.

In addition, the VeriFish framework might convey broader recommendations, such as:

- Recognising that aquafood species are not just as a generic product, but individuals from different species that require distinct management approaches due to their varying biological characteristics¹.
- Understanding that wild-caught fisheries and aquaculture present unique sustainability challenges, even though this might not always be immediately apparent in the products available to consumers.
- Demonstrating how sustainable aquafood can fit in a climate-friendly healthy diet.

Ultimately, the framework is designed to support a more informed and collaborative approach to production and consumption, ensuring that everyone plays their part in protecting aquatic resources for the future.

2.2. Objectives of the Deliverable

The objective of this deliverable (D2.1) is to define a comprehensive indicator framework for aquafood, which integrates the three pillars—environmental, social and economic, and nutrition and health. The framework must support transparent communication about aquafood, specifying the framework structure, data requirements, and prioritising indicators that can be used in communication campaigns, regardless of current availability. D2.1 sets the foundation for using verifiable and qualified information in campaigns designed to support aquafood chain actors to promote informed aquafood consumption amongst consumers.

¹ The difference between fish and fishes is represented by difference in approach between the citizens of megapoles for whom fish (= flesh) = frozen aluminium boxes, necessarily leading to over-exploitation, and people from First Nations who maintain a direct link with fishes (= individual living organism) in nature, encouraging sustainability, although there are exceptions in both cases.

3. Indicators identification and selection

An **ATTRIBUTE** is a specific characteristic or property of an indicator that provides more detailed information and helps in interpretation or assessment. For example, the species attribute refers to type or classification of an aquafood (e.g., Atlantic salmon or *Salmo salar*). This attribute provides critical information for understanding the context of an indicator like stock status, as different species have unique biological, ecological, nutritional, and economic characteristics. Species-level data are essential for accurately assessing sustainability, health impacts, and management strategies in fisheries, since different species respond differently to environmental factors and fishing pressures.

In contrast, an **INDICATOR** is a measurable variable or parameter used to assess and communicate a particular aspect of a system, such as environmental, social, or economic performance. While an attribute contains information/facts about an entity, an indicator uses one or several attributes to provide a measurement. Indicators help simplify complex information, making it easier for stakeholders to make informed decisions. In this case, for example, stock status describes the condition of a fish population in relation to fishing limits. It assesses whether stock is being harvested sustainably or over-fished. Stock status indicators are typically based on scientific data about fish population size, reproductive rates, and impacts of fishing activities. Such indicators help determine whether current practices are depleting the stock or allowing it to recover, and they are vital for promoting sustainable fishery management.

3.1. Attributes: Capture fisheries

Capture fisheries harvest naturally occurring fish from their natural habitats, including oceans, rivers, lakes, and other aquatic environments. These fisheries depend on wild fish populations, making effective management critical to maintaining a balance between resource extraction and the conservation of aquatic ecosystems. To achieve this, detailed records are kept tracking fisheries activities and associated fish stocks.

Key attributes for sustainability of wild-caught seafood

Determining the sustainability of wild-caught seafood products relies on several essential attributes, including species, gear/capture method, and region.

a. Species identification

Accurate species identification is vital, with Latin (scientific) names preferred to avoid confusion caused by regional variations in common names. For fresh seafood products, [Regulation No. 1379/2013](#) mandates the use of scientific names, but various systems are used for species codes, such as:

- Scientific (Binomial) names: Latin names combining genus and epithet, e.g., *Thunnus albacares*

- FAO ASFIS codes²: Three-digit species codes for fishery statistics, e.g., YFT for yellowfin tuna
- Taxonomic systems: Codes like the taxonomic serial number (TSN³) from the integrated taxonomic information system, e.g., 175001002610
- Public species databases: Sources like FishBase, WoRMS, or GBIF.
- [Commercial designations of fishery and aquaculture products](#)

b. Region (Catch Area)

The location where fish are caught (be that an ocean, lake, or river) is crucial for sustainability assessment. Oceanic catch areas are categorised into FAO regions worldwide (e.g., NE Atlantic as FAO 27, Mediterranean as FAO 37) and further divided into smaller GFCM regions (General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean), some designated by ICES (International Council for the Exploration of the Sea), which are mandatory for products caught in European Union waters under [Regulation \(EU\) No 1308/2013](#) (hereafter CMO Regulation). Detailed catch area information is crucial because fishery resources are managed at the stock level, which refers to a subpopulation of a species defined by its specific geographic location, typically corresponding to a division or sub-area. For example, fish from one stock might be overfished or at risk of depletion, whilst the same species in a different region might be abundant and sustainably managed. Distinguishing amongst these stocks allows fisheries managers to implement tailored conservation and management strategies, such as setting region-specific quotas, seasonal closures, or gear restrictions, to ensure that fishing practices do not exceed the reproductive capacity of the stock. Without detailed catch area data, it is impossible to accurately assess sustainability of fishing activities, potentially leading to over-exploitation of vulnerable stocks or mislabelling of products, undermining consumer trust and the credibility of sustainability certifications. In essence, this granularity is critical for maintaining a balance between sustainable resource use and the long-term health of aquatic ecosystems.

c. Gear/Capture Method

Fishing gear has a significant role in sustainability. The FAO International Standard Statistical Classification of Fishing Gear (ISSCFG) categorises fishing equipment into 10 broad groups and 47 gear types ([Classification and illustrated definition of fishing gears](#)). However, within these gear types, there is considerable diversification and descriptions are user-defined. Currently, the CMO Regulation requires seafood producers to report the category of fishing gear used to catch a given product (see Annex III, column 1). However, this classification includes only seven broad categories of fishing gears, which, for instance, group together

² <https://www.fao.org/fishery/en/collection/asfis>

³ <https://www.itis.gov/>

demersal and pelagic trawls under a single category (i.e., Trawls). In addition to this mandatory information (gear category), producers could also provide more detailed data about the fishing gear used (28 gears, see Annex III, column 2). Diversification within gear types and their application, coupled with user-defined descriptions, poses challenges for sustainable fisheries management because gear types have different environmental impacts, including bycatch rates, habitat disruption, and fuel consumption. When more detailed information is left to the discretion of users, inconsistency and ambiguity arise, making it difficult to compare data across fisheries, regions, or datasets. This lack of standardisation undermines evaluation sustainability and effective management measures. Moreover, vague or inconsistent gear classifications can lead to inadequate regulatory oversight, where harmful practices might go unnoticed or unaddressed. It also creates challenges for sustainability certification systems that rely on precise and standardised information to assess the environmental footprint of fishing operations. Without clear descriptions, unsustainable practices might inadvertently receive certification, eroding consumer trust and misrepresenting ecological impact.

Additional attributes for sustainability assessment

Other factors that could enhance sustainability assessment include:

- **Vessel capacity and other specifications:** Attributes like engine power, mesh size, and the flag state of the vessel⁴, although this information is often unavailable unless provided by producers.
- **Management plans:** Management plans for specific products provide assurances that measures are in place to sustainably manage resources. These plans typically incorporate strategies to regulate fishing efforts and promote long-term sustainability, including quotas, seasonal closures, gear restrictions, and total allowable catch limits. By adopting a comprehensive, systematic approach to sustainability, management plans minimise the need for scrutiny of individual attributes, such as vessel capacity, engine power, or mesh size. Instead, they focus on implementing collective measures that ensure responsible and sustainable fishing practices across the board.
- **Ecological considerations:** In data-limited scenarios, attributes like growth rate and trophic level can inform basic management measures. However, these are less relevant for defining sustainability.

3.2. Attributes: Aquaculture

Classifications for aquaculture systems are not as well standardised as for capture fisheries. In terms of their environmental impact, there are two main areas that must be considered, (i) feed input and (ii) connectivity with the external environment.

⁴ Country where a vessel is registered and whose laws govern its operations, including compliance with international, regional, and national fishing regulations.

- (i) Feed inputs, based on FAO documentation⁵, include:
1. **Non-fed extensive systems**⁶ can include seaweed culture, coastal bivalve culture (e.g., mussels, oyster, clams and cockles), coastal fishponds (mulletts, milkfish, shrimps, tilapias) and pen and cage culture in eutrophic waters and/or rich benthos (carps, catfish, milkfish and tilapias).
 2. **Fed extensive systems** can include coastal fishponds (e.g. mullets, milkfish, tilapias) and pen and cage culture in eutrophic waters and/or rich benthos (carps, catfish, milkfish and tilapias). Regardless, volumes of feed used must be very low.
 3. **Semi-intensive systems** are production systems that include fresh and brackish water ponds (shrimps and prawns, carps, catfish, milkfish, mullets and tilapias). In addition, integrated agriculture-aquaculture (rice-fish; livestock/poultry-fish; vegetables - fish and all combinations of these) can be considered as semi-intensive systems. Moreover, sewage-fish cultures, which include waste treatment ponds, latrine wastes and septage used as pond inputs and fish cages in wastewater channels are considered by FAO as semi-intensive systems. Finally, cage and pen cultures, especially in eutrophic waters or on rich benthos (carps, catfish, milkfish, tilapias) are also considered as semi-intensive culture systems.
 4. **Intensive systems** are culture systems where FAO includes freshwater, brackish water and marine ponds (shrimps; fish, especially carnivores - catfish, snakeheads, groupers, sea bass, etc.). Other intensive systems include freshwater, brackish water and marine cage and pen culture (finfish, especially carnivores -groupers, sea bass, etc. - but also some omnivores such as common carp). Moreover, other production systems like raceways, silos, tanks, etc. can be considered as intensive.
 5. **Intermediate forms of production systems** (comprising both aquaculture & fisheries operations, for instance when aquaculture is for stock enhancement or conservation purposes such as restocking).
- (ii) Connectivity with the external environment

STECF (2023⁷) developed a classification of aquaculture production systems based upon EU MAP (EC 2016/1251) to sufficiently discern production siting types, degree of water exchange, water pollution source and production intensity. This also examined the FAO aquaculture system classification under CWP⁸-IS-2022/9 and developed a more globally applicable approach (see Table 1: Aquaculture production system classification and origin).

⁵ Baluyut, E. (1989) [Aquaculture Systems and Practices: A Selected Review](#). ADCP/REP/89/43. FAO, Rome

⁶ For definitions of extensive vs intensive aquaculture, see Oddsson, G.V. (2020). A Definition of Aquaculture Intensity Based on Production Functions—The Aquaculture Production Intensity Scale (APIS). *Water* 2020, 12(3), 765; <https://doi.org/10.3390/w12030765>

⁷ Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries (STECF) (2023). Marketing standards: review of proposed sustainability criteria / indicators for aquaculture (STECF-22-13). Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2023, doi:10.2760/93710, JRC132139

⁸ Coordinating Working Party on Fishery Statistics, see <https://www.fao.org/index.php?id=86726>

Production system	Origin
Ponds (land, based, open)	EU-MAP
Tanks and raceways (land-based, closed)	EU-MAP
Enclosures and pens (open)	EU-MAP
Recirculating systems (land-based, closed)	EU-MAP
Cages (open)	EU-MAP
Off-bottom Rafts (open)	EU-MAP
Off-bottom Longlines (open)	EU-MAP
On-bottom (open)	EU-MAP
Barrages and irrigation systems (open)	FAO-CWP
Lakes, coastal lagoons and other natural water (open)	FAO-CWP
Integrated culture: Rice-Fish culture (open)	FAO-CWP
Integrated culture: Aquaponics (closed)	FAO-CWP
Integrated culture: IMTA (open)	FAO-CWP
Integrated culture: Other polyculture (open)	FAO-CWP
Plastic bags, photobioreactor tubes or panels (closed)	FAO-CWP
Off-bottom Baskets, Net bags, Net trays, Poles (open)	FAO-CWP
Off-bottom lanterns, boxes	FAO-CWP

Table 1: Aquaculture production system classification and origin⁷

Other attributes relevant to aquaculture include:

- a. Environment e.g. whether the species is reared during its grow-out phase in:
 - a. **Marine water** (e.g. full seawater above 30 parts per thousand (‰))
 - b. **Brackish water** (e.g. 0.5 – 30 ‰)
 - c. **Fresh water** (e.g. less than 0.5 ‰).
- b. Alien status e.g. whether the species being reared is:

- a. **Endemic** (e.g. the species is naturally distributed in the location of the aquaculture operation)
- b. **Introduced** (e.g. the species has been anthropogenically introduced to the location of the aquaculture operation)
- c. Production cycle status e.g. whether the aquaculture operation being considered is:
 - a. **Full cycle** (i.e. has been hatchery-bred and grown to final harvest)
 - b. **For restocking** (i.e. hatchery-bred and grown for release into the wild as a stock enhancement exercise - also called ranching); or
 - c. **For grow-out only** (i.e. juveniles are caught in the wild and then grown out to final harvest in captivity).

3.3. Attributes: Nutrition and health

Nutrition attributes help to determine how well a food supports human health, providing insights into dietary choices and public health outcomes. Attributes commonly associated with nutrition and health include:

1. **Macronutrient composition:**
 - a. **Protein:** Amount of protein and quality (e.g., essential amino acids profile)
 - b. **Carbohydrate:** Total carbohydrates, simple sugars, complex carbohydrates, and fibre.
 - c. **Fat:** Total, saturated fat, unsaturated fats (monounsaturated and polyunsaturated), trans fats.
2. **Micronutrient composition:**
 - a. **Vitamins** (e.g., vitamins A, C, D, E, K, and B-complex)
 - b. **Minerals** (e.g., calcium, iron, magnesium, potassium, zinc)
 - c. **Caloric Value or energy**, i.e., calories provided, usually measured in kilocalories (kcal) or kilojoules (kJ) and derived from the macronutrient composition (protein, fat, carbohydrates).
 - d. **Glycaemic index (GI) or load**, which describe effects of foods on blood glucose and insulin concentrations/regulation, reflecting how quickly carbohydrates are digested and absorbed
3. **Fatty acid profile:**
 - a. **Omega-3 and Omega-6 fatty acids content**

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- b. Saturated:unsaturated: ratio of healthy unsaturated fats to saturated fats
4. Bioactive compounds:
 - a. Antioxidants: consumption of polyphenols, flavonoids, carotenoids etc. that are associated with reduced risk of disease likely though lower oxidative stress and inflammation.
 - b. Phytochemicals: plant compounds (e.g., isoflavones, glucosinolates) that are linked to reduced disease risk through mechanisms other than as antioxidants.
 5. Sodium and potassium:
 - a. Sodium content: High sodium intake is linked to hypertension and cardiovascular diseases.
 - b. Potassium content: Helps balance sodium and supports healthy blood pressure.
 6. Allergenicity:
 - a. Food allergens (e.g., fish, shellfish, crustacea) that can cause adverse Ige-mediated reactions in sensitive or allergic individuals.
 7. Digestibility and absorption or bioavailability: extent to which nutrients or bioactive compounds are absorbed and utilised, which can vary based on food processing, preparation, or the presence of compounds including fibre and phytates that inhibit absorption.
 8. Functional health benefits
 - a. Probiotics (beneficial bacteria) and prebiotics (e.g., fibre) that promote gut health.
 9. Nutrient density, i.e., nutrient-to-calorie ratio or concentrations of nutrients relative to the caloric or energy content, reflecting how nutritious/healthy a food is in relation to energy intakes.
 10. Safety and contaminants:
 - a. Harmful contaminants such as heavy metals, pesticides, or foodborne pathogens
 - b. Toxicity, i.e., potential toxic substances (e.g., mercury) that pose a health risk
 11. Dietary suitability:
 - a. Suitability for special diets, i.e., whether a food meets requirements for specific dietary needs, such as low-fat, gluten-free, vegan, vegetarian, etc.
 - b. Fortification/enrichment, i.e., foods to which specific nutrients have been added, such as cereals and milk fortified with vitamins or bread enriched folic acid.
 12. Health and nutrition claims
 - a. Authorised health claims, e.g., "lowers cholesterol" or "supports immune function,"

- b. Authorised nutrition claims, e.g., high-in, free-from, etc.
13. Satiety and appetite control, i.e., extent to which a food satisfies hunger and helps control appetite.

These attributes are central to understanding nutritional quality and aspects of health associated with consumption of foods, enabling individuals to make informed decisions about dietary choices and potential health outcomes. Selection of nutrition and health indicators, therefore, required systematic review to ensure each reflects nutritional quality and health impacts of aquafood, i.e., relevant, measurable, and valid.

3.4. Indicators: Capture fisheries

A suite of 21 indicators were identified as suitable for potential use for wild capture products. These cover a variety of areas, including stock status, climate impact, ecosystem impact, animal welfare, and governance.

a. Stock Status

Stock status of a fish population within a specific fishery and geographic area refers to its current condition relative to established sustainability goals. Assessing stock status is essential for effective fisheries management, as it determines whether fish populations in particular areas are being harvested sustainably or at risk of overfishing, possibly due to factors such as fishing pressure, habitat degradation, and environmental changes. In fisheries biology and economics, maximum sustainable yield (MSY) represents the largest average catch that can theoretically be sustained indefinitely under stable environmental conditions. Typically measured in tonnes, MSY serves as a benchmark for sustainable harvesting practices. To ensure a viable and thriving fishing industry, stock status must remain consistently above those required to produce MSY over the long term. It is also crucial to distinguish between stock biomass (total weight of fish in a population), fishing yield (number of fish harvested by a fishery over a specified period), and fishing rates (intensity of fishing effort over a specified period). Understanding these distinctions is vital for maintaining sustainable fisheries and preventing over-exploitation.

BIOMASS (B) is the weight of all the fish of a specific stock in the water measured in tonnes.

YIELD is the catch, i.e. the fish taken out of the water through fishing measured in tonnes.

FISHING MORTALITY RATE (F) is the catch relative to the size of the stock (proportion of fish caught and removed by fishing).

FISHERY MANAGEMENT PLAN generally is based on harvest control rules, using B and F in relation to MSY,

technical measures and/or spatial closures.

B_{MSY} is the biomass that enables a fish stock to deliver the maximum sustainable yield. In theory, B_{MSY} is the population size at the point of maximum growth rate. The surplus biomass that is produced by the population at B_{MSY} is the maximum sustainable yield that can be theoretically harvested without reducing the population.

F_{MSY} is the maximum fishing mortality (proportion of a fish stock caught and removed by fishing) resulting eventually, usually a very long timeframe, in a population size of B_{MSY} . F_{MSY} is a constant and can be applied to any stock that is not impaired in its reproductive capacity.

MSY , B_{MSY} and F_{MSY} are reference points that are expected to remain fixed unless the environment changes or better data become available. On the other hand, B , Y and F might change every year. In the EU context, they are also corrected backwards in time by the International Council for the Exploration of the Seas (ICES) and FAO-GFCM.

The European Commission considers a fish stock to be overfished when its biomass is below B_{MSY} ⁹. FAO defines a fish population as overfished when its biomass is below 80 percent of the target level ($B/B_{MSY} < 0.8$ ¹⁰). In such a situation, a species stock is unable to produce the maximum sustainable yield (MSY). Overfishing can occur whether a stock is above B_{MSY} or not. Overfishing occurs when more than the sustainable catch is taken out of a given fish stock, i.e. when fishing mortality (F) is above F_{MSY} . Then, biomass of the stock will diminish. If F is less than F_{MSY} , underfishing is happening. Fishing pressure is usually reported as a ratio of F/F_{MSY} , and a ratio greater than 1 means overfishing. To allow an overfished stock to rebuild to B_{MSY} , if the environmental conditions are constant and recruitment to the population has not been impaired, the fishing mortality (F) has to be set at F_{MSY} or below. The lower F , the faster a stock can recover, and the maximum sustainable yield be available again. As the stock grows, fisheries will be rewarded with higher and more stable yields than previously attainable. Fisheries with B/B_{MSY} below 1 (overfished), but with F/F_{MSY} also below 1 (underfishing), are rebuilding. If overfishing continues, a stock can collapse, with serious long-term impacts on the fishing sector and marine environment.

b. Climate impact, as measured by carbon footprint

Environmental impacts of animal protein production are largely influenced by resources required to raise and care for animals. In contrast, wild-caught fish grow and feed naturally, giving them the lowest emissions amongst animal proteins. However, the carbon footprint of seafood varies significantly depending on the species and fishing method used. For example, heavy bottom trawling for flatfish consumes far more fuel per

⁹ Regulation (EU) No 1380/2013 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:32013R1380>

¹⁰ <https://openknowledge.fao.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/66538eba-9c85-4504-8438-c1cf0a0a3903/content/sofia/2024/status-of-fishery-resources.html>

kilogram of landed fish than floating nets to catch a school of herring. In addition to fuel emissions, bottom trawling has a unique environmental impact due to its disturbance of the seafloor. Dragging nets across the seabed disrupts sediments that have stored organic carbon for centuries. When these sediments are disturbed, a portion of the stored carbon is released into the water column and can eventually contribute to atmospheric CO₂. Although exact amounts of "blue carbon" released through bottom trawling remains a topic of scientific debate, its potential impact on the carbon cycle is significant¹¹.

Fisheries with minimal bycatch are generally more fuel-efficient per kilogram of usable product than those with high bycatch, where a portion of the catch is discarded or underutilised. Beyond fishing methods, modes of transport in the seafood supply chain also have a critical role in determining carbon emissions. Frozen seafood transported by container ship, even over long distances such as from Asia to Europe, is relatively fuel-efficient. In contrast, seafood transported by air has a substantially higher carbon footprint. This means locally sourced seafood is not automatically more climate-friendly, particularly if harvested using fuel-intensive methods.

The most suitable metric for assessing climate impact of seafood is CO₂-equivalents (CO₂eq) per Kg of product. To address this, the European Commission is developing product environmental footprint category rules (PEFCR) to standardise calculation and comparisons of environmental impacts across products and services. While these rules are comprehensive and consider multiple factors, they require extensive data, posing challenges for widespread implementation and consider only marine fish whilst crustaceans, molluscs, freshwater fish, and prepared and preserved products are not included.

c. Ecosystem, as measured by seabed impacts

HABITAT AND ECOSYSTEM IMPACT: Fishing methods vary in their impact on marine habitats, which are critical for maintaining biodiversity and supporting healthy fish populations. Habitats such as coral reefs, seagrass beds, and ocean floor structures are especially vulnerable to disruption from certain fishing practices. Assessing these impacts requires an indicator for habitat disturbance, which measures the extent to which fishing activities—like trawling—damage or destroy marine environments. However, there is currently no scientific consensus or standardized method for evaluating fishing impacts on pelagic habitats, leaving gaps in understanding their full ecosystem effects. Different fishing gear types interact with ecosystems uniquely, depending on how and where they are used.

These interactions are typically classified based on habitat type and the severity of physical impact:

¹¹ Sala *et al.* (2021) Protecting the global ocean for biodiversity, food and climate. *Nature* 592, 397–402 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03371-z>; Hiddink *et al.* (2023) Quantifying the carbon benefits of ending bottom trawling. *Nature* 617, E1–E2 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06014-7>

SOFT SEDIMENTS: Habitats like sand and mud are relatively resilient but can be significantly disrupted by heavy gear, causing sediment displacement, smothering, and altered sediment structure.

HARD SUBSTRATES: Rocky reefs and cobble provide shelter for diverse benthic species but are sensitive to physical damage. Gear like trawls can destroy structures and harm slow-growing organisms like sponges and corals.

BIOGENIC HABITATS: Ecosystems like coral reefs, seagrass beds, and kelp forests, formed by living organisms, are particularly fragile. Even minor disturbances can disrupt the balance of these ecosystems, impacting biodiversity.

DEEP-SEA HABITATS: Due to slow recovery rates in cold, low-light environments, deep-sea habitats are highly susceptible to long-term or irreversible damage from gear impacts.

Gear impacts are also categorised by physical contact with the seafloor:

HIGH-IMPACT BOTTOM-CONTACT GEAR: Bottom trawls and dredges cause extensive damage to the seafloor by displacing sediment, destroying benthic organisms, and degrading habitats.

MODERATE-IMPACT GEAR: Set gears like traps, pots, and bottom-contact longlines affect the seafloor to a lesser extent, often causing localised damage rather than widespread disruption.

LOW-IMPACT, MINIMAL-CONTACT GEAR: Pelagic trawls, midwater longlines, and hook-and-line fishing minimize seafloor interaction, reducing habitat damage.

Efforts to quantify these impacts include methodologies like the STECF EWG 22-12 ([EWG report](#)) scoring system, which evaluates fishing gear impact on the seabed based on species and gear type. This tool links habitat types to commercial marine species and provides a proxy for habitat disturbance.

ECOSYSTEM FUNCTIONING: Indicators for ecosystem functioning assess whether fishing activities maintain ecosystem structure, productivity, and overall health. A key measure is the **TROPHIC LEVEL**, which tracks changes in the species caught. Targeting species lower or higher on the food chain can signal shifts in ecosystem balance, leading to cascading effects on biodiversity and productivity.

BYCATCH AND DISCARDS: Bycatch refers to the unintended capture of non-target species, such as other fish, marine mammals, seabirds, and turtles. Bycatch can be categorised as either wanted (retained and utilised) or unwanted (discarded, often dead or dying). Sustainable fisheries aim to minimise bycatch, particularly for threatened and endangered species, to protect biodiversity. Lower discard rates typically indicate more

selective fishing practices. However, in some regions, like Southeast Asia, small-mesh fisheries land all their catch, including bycatch, to reduce waste. Managing bycatch of endangered, threatened, and protected (ETP) species is critical to sustainable fishing. Direct impacts, such as entanglement or death, and indirect effects, like disrupted migration routes or reduced habitats, can threaten the survival of these species. Indicators to measure ETP impacts are being developed but require more detailed spatial and gear-type data, as highlighted by STECF EWG 23-18.

GEAR LOSS AND GHOST GEAR: Abandoned, lost, or discarded fishing gear, often called ghost gear, is one of the most damaging forms of marine pollution. Ghost gear can (i) entangle marine life, trapping fish, sea turtles, dolphins, and whales, often resulting in injury or death; (ii) damage ecosystems, destroying sensitive habitats like coral reefs, which serve as nurseries for marine species; and (iii) contribute to plastic pollution, because most are made from plastics that degrade into microplastics, entering the food chain and impacting marine and human health. Efforts to mitigate ghost gear include retrieval programmes, biodegradable gear designs (e.g., bamboo-based fish aggregating devices), and stricter regulations to hold fishers accountable for lost equipment. International agreements are also working to improve waste management practices within the fishing industry. By addressing these varied impacts, fisheries can better manage their environmental footprint and contribute to the long-term health and sustainability of marine ecosystems.

ANIMAL WELFARE: Welfare is defined as the "*state of an individual in relation to its attempts to cope with its environment*". Unlike aquaculture, where humans are directly responsible for managing rearing conditions, the focus in fisheries lies in minimising physical harm and physiological stress during key stages including underwater capture, handling on deck, and stunning and slaughtering. Welfare considerations in fisheries remain an emerging field, with ongoing research and development aimed at improving practices.

GOVERNANCE: Effective fisheries management strategies must be flexible and adaptive, enabling responses to new scientific data and unexpected changes in fish populations or ecosystem conditions. A robust fisheries management plan (FMP) is essential to ensure the sustainability of fish stocks, marine habitats, and fishing communities. A well-structured FMP incorporates a range of elements to ensure the long-term sustainability of marine resources, protect biodiversity, and support fishing communities. The integration of adaptive management strategies, robust enforcement, and collaborative improvement initiatives forms the foundation for resilient fisheries in the face of environmental and economic challenges.

Key elements of a comprehensive FMP include:

- a. **CATCH LIMITS AND HARVEST STRATEGIES:** To maintain fish populations at sustainable levels, FMPs must include specific targets for stock biomass, mortality rates, and reproduction achieved through:
 - i. **Total allowable catch (TAC)**, which is determined based on indicators such as biomass, fishing pressure, and recruitment levels of a stock. Pre-set harvest control rules (HCRs) guide how much fishing can occur depending on stock status. These rules, based on empirical or model-based indicators, form the operational component of sustainable harvest strategies.

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- ii. **EU quota allocation:** In the EU, TAC is divided amongst Member States using a fixed allocation key known as relative stability, which ensures consistent shares as long as stock geographical distribution remains stable.
 - iii. **Scientific advice** (e.g., ICES, GFCM), helping to align catch limits with annual assessments.
- b. **SCIENTIFIC DATA COLLECTION AND MONITORING:** Regular monitoring of fish populations, recruitment, fishing effort, and bycatch is vital to ensure informed decision-making. Key practices include:
- i. **Mandatory catch reporting** that ensures transparency and accountability.
 - ii. **Data collection on ecosystem health**, which tracks changes in habitats and biodiversity to guide adaptive management decisions.
- c. **HABITAT PROTECTION AND SEASONAL CLOSURES:**
- i. **Marine protected areas** that restrict or prohibit fishing in certain areas to protect habitats and allow fish populations to recover.
 - ii. **Seasonal and spatial closures** implemented during key spawning or migration periods to enhance long-term productivity.
- d. **SELECTIVE GEAR REQUIREMENTS:** Mandatory use of selective fishing gear (e.g., increased codend mesh size, escape panels in nets, species-specific hook sizes) help reduce undersized individuals and unwanted catches.
- e. **ENFORCEMENT AND COMPLIANCE:** Strong regulations and enforcement mechanisms, including penalties and sanctions, are critical to ensuring adherence to quotas and management practices:
- i. **IUU fishing prevention:** Illegal, unreported, and unregulated fishing accounts for up to 20% of the global catch, costing ca. €26-50 billion annually¹². IUU practices threaten [marine biodiversity](#), [exacerbate poverty](#), and [undermine food security](#).
 - ii. **Monitoring tools:** Use of vessel monitoring systems, satellite tracking, and onboard observers helps ensure compliance. Penalties for violations must be clear and enforceable.
- f. **TRACEABILITY AND IUU REGULATIONS:**
- i. **EU IUU Regulation:** Introduced in 2010, Regulation (EC) No 1005/2008 ([updated in 2024](#)) requires all fishery products entering or leaving the EU market to be accompanied by a catch certificate, ensuring traceability and compliance with conservation rules.
 - ii. **Digital Systems (CATCH):** To combat fraud, the EU is transitioning to a digital catch certification system, mandatory from [January 2026](#), to streamline verification processes.

¹² Mackay *et al.*, (2020) The intersection between illegal fishing, crimes at sea, and social well-being. *Frontiers in Marine Science* DOI=10.3389/fmars.2020.589000

g. **INDEPENDENT CERTIFICATION:** Recognised certification schemes, such as the Marine Stewardship Council (MSC) and Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC), provide transparent, science-based evaluations of sustainability. These certifications are built on independent auditing, stakeholder involvement, and continuous improvement standards. However, they are often awarded to fishing collectives, limiting differentiation at the vessel level.

h. **FISHERIES IMPROVEMENT PROGRAMMES (FIPs)** are collaborative initiatives aimed at improving the sustainability and management of fisheries. These programmes vary in scope. Basic FIPs focus on fundamental sustainability practices, with less structured timelines, whilst comprehensive FIPs are designed to achieve certifications like MSC, with clear timelines, transparency, and independent assessments. Credible FIPs are often listed on platforms like [FisheryProgress.org](https://fisheryprogress.org).

VeriFish

The sustainability indicator framework to communicate responsible aquafood production and consumption patterns

Pillar	Sub-pillar	Indicator	Description	T1 data needs	T2 data needs
01 Environment	Stock status	Stock status	Spawning stock biomass (SSB)	GRSF	Not applicable at vessel level
01 Environment	Stock status	Fishing mortality	Fishing mortality is the share of the fish stock that dies annually because of fishing. Expressed in relation to F_{msy} , $F_{trigger}$ etc.	GRSF	Not applicable at vessel level
01 Environment	Stock status	Resilience	Susceptibility to fishing pressure. Especially relevant for data deficient stocks	Resilience score from Fishbase	Not applicable at vessel level
01 Environment	Climate impact	CO2eq/kg landed catch	Output of CO2 equivalent greenhouse gasses per kg landed catch	Typical fuel consumption data per catch method and species	Greenhouse gas emissions of vessel as CO2eq/kg landed product

Pillar	Sub-pillar	Indicator	Description	T1 data needs	T2 data needs
01 Environment	Climate impact	Product Environmental Footprint (PEF)	Environmental footprint for fishery or aquaculture product. A PEF is a standardised LCA study.	PEF category rules for seafood are being developed by DG environment	Company/vessel data based
01 Environment	Ecosystem impact	Habitat impact	Impact on seabed and its community. Scoring through association of species with certain habitat	gear x seabed type proxy. Scoring through association of species with certain habitat	Specific information on fishing location. Related to EUNIS https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/eunis-habitat-classification .
01 Environment	Ecosystem impact	Trophic effects	Ecosystem impacts due to trophic effects. B/Bo: ratio of stock biomass over the mean equilibrium unfished biomass; as a proxy of indirect impacts on prey and predators	Biomass data from GRSF	Not applicable at vessel level
01 Environment	Ecosystem impact	Bycatch	Bycatch of unwanted species and juveniles that are being discarded. Could be expressed as discard ratio (discards/landings)	Amount of discard typical for gear type and landed catch	Amount of discard typical for vessel and landed catch
01 Environment	Ecosystem impact	ETP impact	Impact (due to interaction with) on Endangered, Threatened, Protected species	CITES convention, CMS convention, IUCN red list of threatened species. STECF-EWG 23-18	(Digital) registration of ETP species at vessel level

Pillar	Sub-pillar	Indicator	Description	T1 data needs	T2 data needs
				risk assessment methodology	
01 Environment	Ecosystem impact	Gear loss	Gear-specific relative risk of abandoning, losing and discarding fishing gear, including fish aggregation devices	Gear based risk	Vessel based mitigation measures or plan
01 Environment	Animal welfare	Capture OWI	Welfare issues from the moment a fish encounters gear until it is on board. Expressed in operational welfare indicators.	Generic OWI score for gear operation	OWI Score at vessel level. Or applied extra mitigation measures.
01 Environment	Animal welfare	Handling OWI	Welfare issues from the moment it gets on board till it is killed/dies.	Generic OWI score for gear operation	OWI Score at vessel level. Or applied extra mitigation measures.
01 Environment	Animal welfare	Stunning and killing	Stunning and killing methods (not) applied	Unlikely at generic level. Maybe in future when legally required, then RFMO or region determines	Stunner implemented on board yes/no

Table 2a: Capture fisheries proposed indicators - Environment

Pillar	Sub-pillar	Indicator	Description	T1 data needs	T2 data needs
02 Management	Governance	Monitoring plan	Is there and how comprehensive is the monitoring of the fishery	Level of monitoring. Present, intensity and quality	Not applicable at vessel level
02 Management	Governance	Stock management	How well the stock is managed. To what extent there is an effective management plan.	Information on HCR, TAC sharing agreement and enforcement	Not applicable at vessel level
02 Management	Governance	ETP impact mitigation	Are measures established to mitigate impact on ETP species and are these measures effective	Mandatory measures by regulation	Use of escape panels, pingers. No or adapted FAD's, active avoidance of aggregations
02 Management	Governance	Discards mitigation	Are measures established to minimize discards and are these measures effective	Mandatory measures by regulation	Use of measures on board
02 Management	Governance	Regulatory framework	Is the regulatory framework for the UoA effective in maintaining the integrity of the surrounding habitat and ecosystem ¹³	On government level	Not applicable at vessel level

¹³ Not easily measured and might not be a priority at this stage but is important for other end-users

Pillar	Sub-pillar	Indicator	Description	T1 data needs	T2 data needs
02 Management	Governance	IUU	Risk of illegal, unreported, unregulated fishery	The Global Record of Fishing Vessels, Refrigerated Transport Vessels and Supply Vessels	Future: digitalised proof of uninterrupted AIS
02 Management	Governance	Certification	Is the fishery certified by a recognised independent certification scheme?	GSSI, ISEAL	
02 Management	Governance	Fisheries improvement programme	Is the fishery taking part in a credible fishery improvement programme?	FishSource (SFP), FisheryProgress, MSC Improvement Program	

Table 2b: Capture fisheries proposed indicators - Management

3.5. Indicators: Aquaculture

Although there has been a proliferation of third-party standards for the environmental certification of aquaculture (e.g. the Aquaculture Stewardship Council ASC, Best Aquaculture Practices BAP, Global G.A.P. Aquaculture and Integrated Aquaculture Assurance, etc), as yet there is not a definitive and widely accepted list of indicators for responsibly produced aquaculture products. At the European level, this is being addressed at two levels, via (i) the EU-funded Aquaculture Assistance Mechanism (AAM) and (ii) development of criteria and indicators to incorporate sustainability aspects for seafood products in the marketing standards under the Common Market Organisation by a Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries ([STECF](#)) Expert Working Group (STECF 20-05).

AAM is currently preparing a set of ‘environmental performance indicators’ for aquaculture as part of their advice to DG MARE. These are still in a draft stage but are designed to provide a list of activities that aquaculture producers must record at farm level for the calculation of their environmental footprint (EF) according to the PEF (product environmental footprint) methodology. Around 32 indicators have been developed and will be finalised soon. The main objectives of **STECF EWG (STECF 20-05)** were to identify suitable criteria and indicators and to assess their potential to be incorporated in regulatory marketing standards, ideally for both fishery and aquaculture products (FAPs) on the EU market, independently of their origin (domestic and imports).

It must be noted that the general principle of the system of indicators proposed by EWG 20-05 to be developed for FAP is not based on an absolute scale with sustainable/not sustainable criteria, but is based on a relative scoring system, where a seafood product is assessed to be relatively more / less sustainable than another seafood product across a set of criteria.

EWG recognised that it was necessary to develop two levels of indicators, these being termed ‘System 1’ and ‘System 2’. Under System 1, publicly available information is used. Having a System 2, based on additional information provided by the producers, would allow producers to obtain a more specific, and in cases a higher, sustainability score. This approach is relevant to VeriFish, and has been utilised in the indicators using different terminology to avoid conflation with the STECF work as follows:

TIER 1 DATA: data are sourced from publicly available sources, such as FAO online databases (e.g. via the Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries GRSF), through APIs with ASC and MSC and other open-source data from FishSource, etc. The advantage of this Tier 1 data is that it is both readily available, usually free of cost and is generally widely validated. The weaknesses are that the data might be patchy e.g. not available for all indicators and will generally be high level, this providing only a broad measure of indicator performance.

TIER 2 DATA: data are provided by the FAP value chain, specifically relating to their production methods, products and processes. The advantage of this is that a relatively high degree of granularity can be obtained across the different indicators that can be used to assess the producer’s performance to a reasonable

degree. The disadvantages are that this information may be subject to bias or error and thus needs independent verification, and it will need additional data collection systems to obtain.

A suite of 21 indicators have been identified as suitable for potential use for aquaculture products. These cover a variety of areas, including animal welfare, biosecurity, climate impact, governance, habitat impact, impact on marine food webs, non-target species impact, resource use, and waste and pollution.

Those not already defined above are:

In aquaculture, **biosecurity** refers to practices, protocols, and measures designed to prevent, manage, and mitigate the introduction and spread of infectious diseases, pests, and invasive species within and between aquaculture facilities. It encompasses the protection of cultured aquatic animals, their environment, and associated industries from biological risks that could compromise health, productivity, and sustainability.

Key components of biosecurity in aquaculture include prevention (measures to minimise the risk of disease introduction, such as screening of broodstock, water quality management, and disinfection protocols); containment (strategies to isolate and control potential outbreaks, including quarantine areas and physical barriers); monitoring and surveillance (regular health checks and testing to detect early signs of disease or contamination); response and management (rapid and coordinated actions to address disease outbreaks or biosecurity breaches, including treatment and culling if necessary); and training and awareness on best practices and the importance of biosecurity.

Effective biosecurity ensures the health of aquatic stocks, protects the surrounding environment, reduces economic losses, and supports the long-term sustainability of aquaculture operations.

Impact on **marine food webs from aquaculture** refers to the alterations in the natural interactions and balance among marine organisms caused by aquaculture activities. These impacts can influence predator-prey relationships, nutrient cycling, and overall ecosystem structure, with potential consequences for biodiversity and ecosystem services. Ways in which aquaculture affects marine food webs include:

- a. **Feed dependency:** Many aquaculture systems, particularly those farming carnivorous species, rely on fishmeal and fish oil derived from wild-caught forage fish. Overharvesting of these species can reduce food availability for natural predators, disrupting the food web.
- b. **Nutrient enrichment (eutrophication):** Uneaten feed and waste from aquaculture facilities can increase nutrient concentrations in surrounding waters, promoting algal blooms. This can alter the base of the food web, often favouring fast-growing, opportunistic species over native ones.
- c. **Predation and competition:** Escaped farmed species can compete with wild counterparts for food and habitat or act as predators especially in ecosystems where they are non-native, causing shifts in food web dynamics.

- d. **Benthic community changes:** Organic waste accumulation beneath aquaculture facilities can smother seafloor habitats, altering benthic communities that are integral to the food web.
- e. **Introduction of non-native species:** Farming of non-native species can lead to the establishment of invasive populations that outcompete or prey upon native species, altering local food web interactions.

Understanding and mitigating these impacts are crucial for sustainable aquaculture practices that maintain the integrity of marine food webs and the ecosystems they support.

In aquaculture, **non-target species impact** are the unintended effects of farming activities on species that are not directly involved in the aquaculture process, which can arise from interactions between aquaculture operations and local ecosystems, often leading to ecological imbalance or harm to biodiversity. Examples of non-target species impact include (i) bycatch in feed harvesting (i.e., unintentionally capture non-target marine species during collection of wild fish for fishmeal and fish oil production, affecting biodiversity and ecosystem health); (ii) predator interactions (i.e., facilities might attract predators, such as seabirds, seals, or otters, which can become entangled in netting, injured, or killed); (iii) habitat alteration of non-target species, such as seagrass beds, mangroves, or coral reefs, which serve as critical nurseries and feeding grounds; (iv) disease and parasite transmission from farmed species can spread to wild populations of non-target species; (v) chemical pollution arising from the use of antibiotics, pesticides, or other chemicals can affect non-target species in surrounding ecosystems, potentially harming sensitive organisms or altering ecological dynamics; and (vi) escaped aquaculture species might outcompete or prey upon non-target native species. Addressing non-target species impacts is an essential aspect of sustainable aquaculture to ensure minimal disruption to surrounding ecosystems and biodiversity.

In aquaculture, **waste and pollution** refer to byproducts and contaminants generated by farming operations that can affect the surrounding environment, ecosystems, and water quality. These impacts arise from uneaten feed, excreted nutrients, chemical use, and structural waste, potentially leading to ecological imbalances and long-term environmental degradation. Managing waste and pollution is crucial for environmental sustainability of aquaculture operations, as well as healthy ecosystems.

For each indicator, Tier 1 and Tier 2 data needs are provided.

Pillar	Sub-pillar	Indicator	Description	T1 data needs	T2 data needs
01 Environment	Animal welfare	Eyestalk ablation used (Y/N/na)	Whether one or more eyestalks are removed to stimulate the female shrimp to induce spawning.	Not possible to score at T1	Producer policy and practices.
01 Environment	Biosecurity	Use of genetically modified organisms (GMOs) in feed materials (Y / N / na)		Permitted / not permitted by national legislation	Producer records, probably on an annual basis
01 Environment	Climate impact	Green-house gases (GHG) potential	From LCA studies or on farm assessments e.g. kg CO2/tonne production	Score based on LCA reviews per production system / species	Specific data collected at the farm level determining farm gate GHGs.
01 Environment	Governance	Third party environmental certification (Y / N / na)	e.g. ASC, GLOBALGAP. Etc	Not possible to score at T1	Production unit(s) covered by a valid certificate.
01 Environment	Habitat impact	Habitat alteration for site (Y / N / na)	Temporal? Recoverability	Farm situated in a protected area	Significant habitat alteration that would require a formal restoration plan.
01 Environment	Impact on marine food webs	Escape potential (% / na)	Generated by standard aqua variables e.g. open/closed, land-based / open water, native / exotic / introduced, species	Generated by standard aqua variables e.g. open/closed, land-based / open water, native / exotic / introduced, species	Producer records, probably on an annual basis

Pillar	Sub-pillar	Indicator	Description	T1 data needs	T2 data needs
01 Environment	Non target species impact	No of birds / animals killed per tonne of production (individuals / tonne)		Farm situated in a SPA (EU only)	Producer records, probably on an annual basis
01 Environment	Non target species impact	Origin of juveniles (wild-caught / hatchery reared / natural spat)	Aqua GRIS FAO	Not possible to score at T1	Producer confirmation
01 Environment	Resource use	Freshwater use (Y/N or m ³ / tonne production)		Open freshwater system (Y/N)	m ³ / water per tonne production.
01 Environment	Resource use	Food conversion ratio (kg growth per kg feed)		Fed species (Y / N)	Producer records, probably on an annual basis
01 Environment	Waste & pollution	Effluents released externally	Generated by standard aqua variables e.g. open/closed, fed/non-fed, species. Mitigation in place e.g. IMTA? Suspended solids (nutrients later)	Fed species (Y / N)	From Marine PEFCR feed emission mass balance model. Remediation / sensitivity.
01 Environment	Waste & pollution	Circularity: proportion plastics reused / recycled (%)	Proportion of annual plastic replaced that are reused / recycled. SUP / MUP used per t prod? Against benchmarks. Released and use separate indicators	National-level compliance with relevant international legislation e.g. EPR, SUP, PRF. (Y/N)	Single-use plastics & multi-use plastics: Weight purchased as a proportion of weight responsibly reused or recycled on an annual basis.

Table 3a: Aquaculture proposed indicators - Environment

Pillar	Sub-pillar	Indicator	Description	T1 data needs	T2 data needs
02 Management	Animal welfare	Survival rate (%). Over grow-out to harvest	% of animals that survive from initial post-nursery stocking to final harvest	Published statistics for key species / system combinations, probably at national level.	Producer records, probably on an annual basis
02 Management	Animal welfare	Stunning (Y / N / na)	Stunned or not at harvest prior to dispatch.	Required / not required by national legislation	Producer policy and practices.
02 Management	Animal welfare	Stocking density (kg/m ³)	Maximum stocking density during the grow-out phase.	Published statistics for key species / system combinations, probably at national level.	Producer records, probably on an annual basis
02 Management	Biosecurity	Antimicrobial therapeutic treatments used (y / n / na)	Available statistics on use per species and production system. Prophylactic or reactive. Use of probiotics?	Available statistics by country on use per species and production system.	Producer records, probably on an annual basis
02 Management	Governance	Robust environmental impact assessment (EIA) required (Y / N / na)	Comprehensive and systematic evaluation of the potential environmental effects of a proposed project, ensuring thorough consideration of all significant impacts and mitigation measures.	Required / not required by national legislation	Robust EIA is publicly available
02 Management	Governance	Area-based management in place (Y / N / na)	Area management plan in place inc. carrying capacity / cumulative impact assessments and resultant management measures.	Required / not required by national legislation	Same as T1.

Pillar	Sub-pillar	Indicator	Description	T1 data needs	T2 data needs
02 Management	Habitat impact	Country-level compliance with international agreements related to protected areas (Y / N / na)	International agreements include the Ramsar Convention, the Convention on Biological Diversity, etc.	National-level compliance with relevant international legislation	Same as T1.
02 Management	Resource use	Use of wild marine species in feeds (yes / no / %?)	From (un)sustainable fisheries. Fish in / Fish out?	Fed species (Y / N)	Producer records on feeds used and % marine ingredients. Could considered higher risk based on stock status / ETP use.
02 Management	Resource use	Use of agriculture ingredients in feeds (yes / no / %?)		Fed species (Y / N)	Producer records on feeds used and % agriculture ingredients. Could considered higher risk based on suite of soy or palm oil.

Table 3b: Aquaculture proposed indicators - Management

The indicators for capture fisheries and aquaculture were selected based on their capacity to measure sustainability effectively and to align with established sustainability frameworks. The selection process involved defining metrics, performance indicators, and indices, which together provide a structured approach to assessing environmental, social, and economic dimensions of aquafood production.

The methodology followed the DIK(U)W hierarchy (data, information, knowledge, understanding, and wisdom), which emphasises transforming raw data into actionable insights. Metrics, such as catch volume or emissions, were used as foundational elements. These were aggregated into performance indicators, such as biomass at maximum sustainable yield (B_{MSY}) or feed conversion ratios (FCR), to offer measurable and comparative assessments of sustainability practices. These indicators were further aligned with specific sustainability targets, ensuring they provided actionable benchmarks for improvement. The driver-pressure-state-impact-response (DPSIR) model guided indicator selection by categorising each as drivers (e.g., market demand), pressures (e.g., fishing intensity), states (e.g., stock health), impacts (e.g., ecosystem disruption), and societal responses (e.g., policy changes). These categories allowed for a comprehensive evaluation of sustainability across ecological, operational, and societal dimensions.

Finally, the indicators were also mapped to existing datasets, including the GRSF, FishBase, and certification schemes, ensuring that they were grounded in accessible and reliable data sources. This approach facilitated the development of indicators that are both scientifically robust and practically applicable, enabling stakeholders to assess and improve sustainability in capture fisheries and aquaculture effectively.

3.6. Indicators: Nutrition and health

The purpose and context of potential indicators were investigated by building reasonable pairs of the terms nutrition/health/contaminants and aquaculture/fishery/human, resulting in (i) nutrition-aquaculture and (ii) health-aquaculture, and (iii) nutrition-human, (iv) contaminants-human, and (v) health human, were defined.

Capture fisheries were not included because there is no human intervention in terms of the nutrient composition of their food and impacts on their health is not directly measurable. Ultimately, nutrition and health for aquaculture, meaning feeding in aquaculture, were also rejected, as these are not directly related to human nutrition and health, the intended pillar of the VeriFish framework. Similarly, human health attributes were rejected as indicators, although they have an important role in justifying individual nutrient indicators (i.e., attributes). Contaminants (aquaculture and human) were both rejected, because it is not appropriate for VeriFish to provide information that might contradict national food authorities and EFSA.

Broadly, attributes were converted to measurable aspects of nutrition (i.e., nutrients rather than bioactive compounds) and relevance determined based on health impact (e.g., high quality protein), which can be

monitored (e.g., reducing malnutrition, promoting heart health, or assessing quality of dietary intake) in any target population (e.g., older adults), and are associated with policy objectives or health goals, such as improving dietary patterns, reducing the prevalence of diet-related diseases, or increasing nutrient intake (i.e., older adults, intake of high quality easily digestible protein). In fisheries – for example – species is an attribute but not an indicator: stock status is the indicator because it can be measured for a species. In nutrition and health indicators protein or sodium content are indicators, because they can be measured using established analytical methods and monitored over time whilst the attribute would be the species. Similarly, indicators were selected based on availability of reliable, standardised methods for measurement across different settings and, finally, data availability, i.e., attributes for which data are available or can be collected (e.g., macronutrient content or micronutrient concentrations available from food composition datasets). Potential indicators were further refined based on scientific validity and evidence supporting a meaningful biological relationship with health outcomes (e.g., omega-3 fatty acids and heart health in adults). Two related issues were also considered, sensitivity and specificity. Chosen indicators needed to be sufficient sensitive and specific for changes in diet or health outcomes to be detected (e.g., blood cholesterol).

Given the complexity for the indicator framework, selected nutrition and health indicators needed to be easily understood by actors in the various aquafood chains and easily communicated to the public as well as consistent with existing public health advice, such as daily recommended intakes. Further, these indicators must provide information that can guide action or decision-making, e.g., high in omega-3 fatty acids for heart health. Other factors that were also considered included (i) time-sensitivity (i.e., indicators that can be tracked over time, such as reductions in sodium intake or increased vitamin D intake), providing insights into the effectiveness of interventions or policy changes; (ii) comparability (i.e., comparisons across different populations, regions, or time periods); (iii) feasibility and cost; and (iv) alignment with policy and global standards (e.g., World Health Organization, Food and Agriculture Organization, or EFSA).

Detailed example of indicator selection process for protein

Purpose: muscle growth and maintenance

Relevance: High-quality protein is essential for tissue repair, muscle growth, and immune function. Aquafoods provide complete proteins, containing all essential amino acids in the right proportions for human health.

Public health relevance: With growing interest in sustainable and healthful protein sources, tracking high-quality protein intake from aquafood can inform dietary guidelines and promote healthier protein choices.

Measurability: Protein content in aquafood is easily ‘measurable’ (calculated) in grams per 100 g edible portion serving. Additionally, quality of protein can be assessed based on amino acid or protein digestibility-corrected amino acid scores.

Data availability: Most food composition datasets provide protein content for various aquafood species, and data on amino acid profiles are typically available for high-protein foods like fish and shellfish.

Scientific validity: Robust scientific evidence that aquafood is rich in high-quality protein. Studies have demonstrated that aquafood proteins, such as those from fish (e.g., salmon, cod) and shellfish (e.g., shrimp, mussels), are easily digestible and contain all essential amino acids.

Biological relevance: Quality of protein in aquafood is important for meeting human nutritional requirements, particularly in populations at risk of protein deficiency or individuals with higher protein needs.

Sensitivity and specificity: Changes in aquafood consumption patterns or protein content can be tracked through dietary surveys or food consumption records. Calculating protein content of aquafoods specifically means the indicator reflects nutritional quality and specific benefits associated with aquafood.

Simplicity and clarity: High-quality protein is easily understood and communicate to actors in the food chain and consumers alike as well as policymakers. It highlights the health benefits of aquafood as a superior protein source. Promoting high-quality protein from aquafood as part of a balanced diet is actionable advice for individuals and public health campaigns.

Time-sensitivity: High-quality protein can be tracked over time to assess trends in consumption and protein intakes, helping evaluate the effectiveness of campaigns promoting aquafood consumption.

Comparability: Protein content allows comparisons across different types of aquafood, countries, or populations to evaluate high-quality protein consumption. It can also be compared with other protein sources (e.g., meat, plant-based products) to assess overall dietary protein quality.

Standardisation & harmonisation: Protein content and quality in aquafoods are standardised and harmonised in food composition databases (FCDBs), making this indicator comparable across studies and regions.

Feasibility and cost: Data on protein content in aquafood is widely available, and the cost of monitoring consumption is relatively low using existing dietary survey tools. The cost of implementing this indicator, especially in public health monitoring, is reasonable, given the existing national food consumption studies.

Alignment with policy and global standards: Protein content aligns with global nutrition recommendations from the WHO, FAO and EFSA, which encourage consumption of high-quality protein sources, including aquafood. Monitoring protein intake from aquafood supports national dietary guidelines promoting the health benefits of aquafood, particularly for populations with increased protein needs (e.g., children, elderly, pregnant women).

Criteria	Comments
Purpose	Track high-quality protein intake from aquafood
Relevance	Complete source of all essential amino acids
Measurability	Quantifiable using FCDB & amino acids or protein digestibility-corrected amino acid scores
Validity	Strong evidence supporting benefits of high-quality protein for human health
Actionable	Increase high-quality protein intake by eating more fish and shellfish
Feasibility	Protein content is widely available and can be tracked through dietary surveys

Table 4. Summary of indicator selection for high-quality protein in aquafood

This process was repeated for each of the attributes identified resulting a list of indicators that were also scored based on priority (1 – highest to 3- lowest, 0-no relevance) as relevant to aquafood composition.

PRIORITY	INDICATOR	DESCRIPTION
0	Trans fatty acids	Trans fatty acids; unhealthy fats created by hydrogenating vegetable oils; associated with an increased risk of heart disease.
0	Water	Essential nutrient for hydration, temperature regulation, nutrient transport, etc.
1	Carbohydrate	Macronutrient that provides energy
1	Cholesterol	Waxy, fat-like substance present in cell membranes and involved in hormones and vitamin D production
1	Chloride	Electrolyte that helps maintain fluid balance, blood pressure, and proper muscle and nerve function
1	Energy	Caloric content provided by macronutrients (carbohydrates, fats, proteins)
1	Monounsaturated fatty acids	Monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFAs); healthy fats with one double bond; associated with reduced risk of CVD
1	Saturated fatty acids	Saturated fatty acids; fats with no double bonds between carbon atoms; typically solid at room temperature, found in animal products and some plant oils.
1	Fat	Macronutrient that provides energy, supports cell growth; essential for absorption and storage of fat-soluble vitamins
1	Iodine	I; mineral necessary for thyroid hormone production

PRIORITY	INDICATOR	DESCRIPTION
1	Sodium	Na; electrolyte that regulates fluid balance, blood pressure, and nerve and muscle function
1	Protein	Macronutrient made of amino acids, essential for building and repairing tissues, enzymes, hormones, and immune function
1	Selenium	Se; mineral with bioactive properties, important for thyroid function and immune system support
1	EPA 20:5(n-3)	Eicosapentaenoic acid; long-chain omega-3 fatty acid found in fish; associated with reduced risk of CVD and inflammation
1	DHA 22:6(n-3)	Docosahexaenoic acid; long-chain omega-3 fatty acid found in fish; essential for brain development and function, and eye health
2	Biotin	B-vitamin (B7) essential for metabolism, fatty acid synthesis, and maintaining healthy skin and hair
2	Calcium	Ca; mineral crucial for bone health, muscle function, nerve signalling, and blood clotting
2	Carotenoids	Pigments found in plants that can be converted to vitamin A in the body and are bioactive
2	Copper	Cu; mineral important for iron metabolism, immune function, and formation of red blood cells and connective tissue
2	Iron	Fe; mineral essential for forming haemoglobin in red blood cells, transporting oxygen, and supporting metabolism and immunity
2	Folate	Folate and/or folic acid; B-vitamin (B9) essential for DNA synthesis, cell division, and fetal development
2	Potassium	K; electrolyte that helps maintain fluid balance, supports muscle contractions, and regulates nerve signals and blood pressure
2	Magnesium	Mg; mineral involved in over enzymatic reactions, including energy production, protein synthesis, and muscle and nerve function
2	Manganese	Mn; mineral that has a role in bone formation, blood clotting, etc.
2	Niacin	B-vitamin (B3) essential for energy metabolism, DNA repair, and maintaining healthy skin and nerves
2	Phosphorus	P; mineral vital for bone and teeth formation, energy production, and cell membrane function

PRIORITY	INDICATOR	DESCRIPTION
2	Pantathenic acid	B-vitamin (B5) crucial for synthesizing and metabolising proteins, carbohydrates, and fats
2	Retinol	Form of vitamin A important for vision, immune function, and skin health
2	Riboflavin	B-vitamin (B2) essential for energy production, red blood cell formation, and the metabolism of fats, some medicines and steroids
2	Thiamin	B-vitamin (B1) essential for energy metabolism and the proper functioning of the nervous system
2	Vitamin A	Fat-soluble vitamin important for vision, immune function, and cell growth
2	Vitamin B12	B-vitamin necessary for red blood cell formation, DNA synthesis, and nervous system function
2	Vitamin B6	B-vitamin (B6) involved in protein metabolism, red blood cell production, and neurotransmitter synthesis
2	Vitamin C	Ascorbic acid; bioactive water-soluble vitamin , essential for collagen synthesis, immune function, and wound healing
2	Vitamin D	Fat-soluble vitamin important for calcium absorption, bone health, and immune function
2	Vitamin E	Fat-soluble vitamin with bioactive properties, protecting cells from damage and supporting immune function
2	Zinc	Zn; mineral crucial for immune function, wound healing, DNA synthesis, and cell division
3	Ash	Inorganic mineral residue left after the complete combustion of organic matter in food
3	Polyunsaturated fatty acids	Polyunsaturated fatty acids(PUFAs); healthy fats with multiple double bonds; associated with reduced risk of CVD

Table 5. Summary of nutrition indicators for aquafood

Prior to review, the roles of selected indicators were analysed within the DPSIR framework, which allows for a structured approach to understanding relationships amongst factors (nutrients or measures of health) and their effects on the system being studied, in this case sustainable aquafood provision in Europe.

DRIVERS represent underlying socio-economic and environmental forces (e.g., increased demand for aquafood driving aquaculture expansion) whilst **PRESSURES** are direct effects of these drivers, such as overfishing,

pollution, or habitat destruction. **STATE** refers to current condition of the environment or resource, which can be measured using selected indicators. **IMPACT** encompasses the consequences of changes, such as loss of biodiversity or reduced ecosystem services, and **RESPONSE** includes policies or actions taken to mitigate negative impacts, such as more sustainable fishing regulations or greater conservation efforts. By mapping selected indicators into this framework, it must become clearer how changes in one part of the system (e.g., overfishing) lead to measurable changes in another (e.g., stock depletion), and what actions (responses) are needed to address these issues. Generally, this approach allows for a comprehensive view of how different factors are interconnected, guiding decision-making and policy intervention.

In aquaculture nutrition, nutrients in feed are not drivers, but activities that produce or use these compounds might be drivers. Likewise, nutrients might not directly create environmental pressures, but their extraction, synthesis or waste streams can have impacts (e.g., omega3 extraction from fish can lead to overfishing, disrupting marine ecosystems; saturated fats and phospholipids derived from palm oil or animal sources might drive deforestation and habitat loss; or trimethylamine oxide production and accumulation in aquatic environments can be a pressure related to fishing and waste disposal). Here, state refers to conditions arising because of these pressures, such as excess or discharge of nutrients in the environment affecting water quality or accumulation of minerals or phospholipids in water or soil, altering nutrient balance and affecting aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems. Nutrients might also impact ecosystems depending on their concentration and persistence (e.g., trimethylamine oxide can contribute to formation of unpleasant odours in water bodies, affecting aquatic life; saturated fats in wastewater can clog sewage systems and create fatbergs, leading to infrastructural and environmental issues; and excess minerals can lead to eutrophication, reducing oxygen levels in water bodies and harming aquatic organisms). Actions taken to manage or mitigate impacts (response) might be regulations on the extraction and discharge of compounds, sustainable practices (voluntary or mandatory), limits on the use in manufacturing, or alternative sources (e.g., plant-based).

In comparison, in the human food chain, demand for balanced nutrition and health or desire for a healthy diet rich in nutrients drive consumption of some foods as might public health guidelines and recommendations, which encourage intakes of specific nutrients (e.g., Ca, Fe, omega-3 fatty acids), influencing consumption patterns, in this case increased consumption of foods rich in the nutrients such as fish and seafood. However, cultural and societal preferences also drive consumption of specific foods (e.g., high fish consumption in coastal regions providing DHA and EPA; ethnic and traditional foods based on local aquafoods). Pressures include over-consumption (of energy, saturated fats, trans fats, (LDL) cholesterol, and salt (sodium), which increase risk (individuals) and morbidity (population) of CVD, obesity, hypertension, etc. Similarly, deficiency of nutrients, especially micronutrients (e.g., I, Fe, Ca, vitamin D, B12) lead to anaemia, osteoporosis, goitre, impaired immune function, etc. putting pressure on the system to supply more foods naturally rich in these nutrients, or foods fortified with these compounds. Production of nutrient-rich foods can exert pressures on the environment through overfishing, land use, water consumption, and greenhouse gas emissions, and production of vitamins and minerals can lead to environmental degradation.

Health and nutritional status of the population, as measured by – for example – body mass index (BMI), plasma and cell micronutrient concentrations, cholesterol concentrations, or the prevalence of health issues (e.g., malnutrition, obesity, CVD) reflect the state of the system from the human perspective whilst changes in fish stocks, water quality, etc. due to production foods rich in these compounds mirror the wider environment. Positive impacts from adequate intake of nutrients are reduced occurrence of diseases, fewer sick days, etc. and negative health impacts from excess or deficiency of nutrients include higher morbidity and mortality, especially premature death (i.e., before 75 years of age). Societal impacts are economic (i.e., healthcare costs, days lost to sickness) and societal, such as increased awareness of nutrition or shifts in dietary patterns. Responses include revised public health policies and dietary guidelines, particularly development and promotion of dietary guidelines that recommend balanced intake of nutrients (e.g., higher intake of omega-3 fatty acids), or fortification of foods with hard-to-obtain or retain nutrients to address common deficiencies. It might also be changes to regulations, limiting unhealthy nutrients (e.g., trans fats, sodium) in processed foods or promoting sustainable fishing and aquaculture practices to minimise environmental impact whilst still meeting nutritional needs as well as public campaigns to promote understanding of the benefits and risks associated with nutrients, emphasising balanced nutrition, and importance of consuming diverse foods, etc.

3.7. Social and economic indicators

Social indicators are metrics that assess social dimensions of aquaculture and fisheries practices, focusing on the well-being of people involved in or affected by these industries. These indicators help evaluate how aquaculture and fisheries production contribute to social equity, community health, labour conditions, and overall societal benefits. However, currently, VeriFish lacks expertise in social indicators. These indicators will be addressed with representatives from the Advisory Board (e.g., Community Catch) and considering recommendations from other organisations (e.g., [International Labour Organization](https://www.ilo.org/)) to identify key attributes and develop appropriate social indicators that might be included in the VeriFish framework. Subsequently, appropriate social and economic indicators will be defined and integrated into D2.2 Indicator Framework developed (M12, FORTH), ensuring social sustainability is a component of the prototype in M12.

Social and economic indicators typically include:

1. Labour Practices and Rights, i.e., treatment of workers, including:

- Wages and working conditions
- Workers' rights and union representation
- Elimination of child labour and forced labour
- Compliance with international labour standards and laws

2. Health and Safety of Workers

- Workplace safety protocols and training
- Access to healthcare and medical facilities
- Accident and injury rates

3. Community Impact and Engagement

- Job creation and income generation for local populations
- Involvement of local communities in decision-making processes
- Access to education and skill development opportunities related to aquaculture and fisheries
- Contributions to local infrastructure and social services

4. Sex Equality and Inclusion (e.g., gender)

- Equal opportunities for men and women in employment, leadership, and ownership
- Policies that promote gender equality and diversity
- Initiatives to empower underrepresented groups in aquaculture and fisheries

5. Food Security and Nutritional Contribution, i.e., access to safe, nutrition and affordable food

- Local availability of affordable and nutritious seafood products
- Contribution of aquaculture and fisheries to reducing hunger and malnutrition, especially in vulnerable populations
- Community reliance on aquaculture and fisheries for dietary needs

6. Cultural and Traditional Practices

- Respect for indigenous and traditional fishing practices
- Integration of local knowledge in sustainable management practices
- Support for maintaining cultural values tied to seafood production and consumption

7. Fair Trade and Ethical Sourcing

- Certification of Fair Trade practices
- Ethical sourcing agreements that benefit small-scale producers
- Policies that promote transparency in product labelling and origin

3.8. Indicators for sustainability of aquafood products

Life cycle analysis (LCA) is a systematic method used to evaluate the environmental impacts associated with all stages of a product life cycle, from raw material extraction, production, and use and disposal or recycling. It provides a comprehensive view of the resource use, energy consumption, and emissions associated with a product or service, helping identify areas for improvement and supporting sustainable decision-making. LCA is widely used across industries to promote sustainability, reduce environmental footprints, and comply with regulations, aligning with broader goals such as the circular economy and climate change mitigation.

LCA and assessment of environmental impacts in capture fisheries or aquaculture share the goal of understanding and mitigating the environmental consequences of human activities, but differ significantly in their approach, scope, and application. LCA takes a comprehensive and systematic approach, evaluating environmental impacts across the entire life cycle of a product or process, from raw material extraction to disposal or recycling. In the context of fisheries or aquaculture, LCA might analyse everything from the production of fishing gear or aquaculture feed to the energy used in transportation and processing, as well as waste generated. This method provides a holistic view, quantifying impacts such as greenhouse gas emissions, water usage, and eutrophication, across all stages of a product. By focusing on the broader system, LCA identifies opportunities for sustainability improvements not only within the fishing operations but throughout the supply chain. Furthermore, environmental impacts of producing aquafood eaten as sourced (e.g., whole fish) can be expected to differ from those of a processed product (e.g., fish pie).

Traditional environmental impact assessments in capture fisheries or aquaculture are often more localised and operational in focus. These assessments examine specific environmental concerns, such as overfishing, bycatch, habitat destruction, or water pollution from aquaculture farms. They aim to address immediate and site-specific ecological issues, emphasising biodiversity, resource depletion, and ecosystem health within a particular geographic area. While these assessments provide critical insights into the direct ecological effects of fisheries and aquaculture activities, they typically do not account for upstream and downstream processes, such as the production of inputs like fishmeal or the energy used in production and transport of aquafoods to markets. Thus, the distinction lies in the breadth of analysis. LCA seeks to provide a quantitative, system-wide perspective, integrating data across multiple sectors and life cycle stages. It informs broader decision-making processes, such as designing more sustainable products, optimizing supply chains, or shaping policies. On the other hand, environmental impact assessments in fisheries and aquaculture often adopt a narrower focus, addressing specific ecological challenges and guiding immediate management decisions to promote sustainable practices within the industry. Both approaches are valuable and complementary. LCA offers a macro-level understanding of sustainability, while traditional environmental assessments provide critical micro-level insights into the direct impacts of fisheries and aquaculture on local ecosystems.

Like social and economic indicators, however, VeriFish lacks expertise in LCA. These indicators will be addressed with representatives from the Advisory Board (e.g., Community Catch) and other initiatives (e.g.,

[Aligned](#), Aalborg University - DK) to identify attributes and appropriate indicators that might be included. Subsequently, appropriate LCA indicators, where possible, will be defined and integrated into D2.2 Indicator Framework developed (M12, FORTH), ensuring social sustainability is a component of the prototype in M12.

Types of LCA that might be relevant to VeriFish include: cradle-to-grave (environmental impact from raw material extraction to disposal); cradle-to-gate (environmental impacts from raw material extraction to the point a product leaves the manufacturing site); gate-to-gate (environmental impact of a single stage in a production process); economic input-output (environmental impacts across an entire supply chain); attributional (environmental impact based on current processes and technologies); consequential (environmental impacts of changes in a product system, including indirect effects); hybrid (combines process-based and economic input-output methods for a more comprehensive assessment); social (social and socio-economic impacts of a product throughout its lifecycle); organisational (life cycle impacts of an organisation); and product carbon footprint, which analyses the greenhouse gas emissions. Alignment will be sought with the ongoing effort to define EU product environmental footprint category rules (PEFCR¹⁴) for seafood and other relevant initiatives, such as development of climate impact tools by MSC and ASC.

3.9. Sources of data: Capture Fisheries

Drafting sustainability indicators for fisheries is a relatively straightforward process; however, finding databases that directly align with these indicators presents a greater challenge. STECF has addressed this issue through a series of reports focusing on criteria and indicators to incorporate sustainability aspects into seafood marketing standards under the CMO. These reports aimed to develop indicators suitable for implementation in semi-automated systems, leading to a tiered framework for data use and evaluation.

STECF EWG 20-05 report, followed by EWG 22-12 and EWG 23-18, introduced two indicator levels. Tier 1 relies on data that must be provided by producers, based on requirements of the CMO Regulation, offering high coverage of fishery products but potentially limited granularity. Tier 2, in contrast, uses data that can be provided voluntarily by value chain actors, offering more detailed assessments but requiring robust independent verification to mitigate biases and errors. EWG 20-05 laid the groundwork by proposing transparent, scientifically sound, and verifiable methods for assessing sustainability aspects of fisheries and aquaculture products along the supply chain. Application of this approach in VeriFish includes Tier 1 data from publicly accessible databases including FAO Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries ([GRSF](#); Tier 1) and, in the future, DG Mare as well as [FishSource](#) (Tier 2). These data are advantageous because of their availability, cost-effectiveness, and validation but provide only broad performance measures.

¹⁴ <https://www.marinefishpefcr.eu>

GRSF is a critical tool for global monitoring, harmonising data from sources like FAO Fisheries and Resources Monitoring System ([FIRMS](#)), RAM Legacy Stock Assessment [database](#), and [IUCN Red List](#), which comprises more than 8,600 stock records and 22,500 fishery records, providing a standardised foundation for sustainability assessments. Complementary datasets, such as the EUNIS habitat classification [database](#), further enhance the capacity to monitor and evaluate sustainability across fisheries and aquaculture sectors. This evolving framework of tiered indicators and integrated sources represents a significant step in measuring and communicating sustainability of aquafood products. However, ongoing refinement and testing will be essential to ensure these effectively support sustainable practices throughout the aquafood supply chain.

3.10 Sources of data: Aquaculture

As discussed above (3.3. Aquaculture indicators), indicators can be categorised as Tier 1 or Tier 2. Like capture fisheries, Tier 1 data, which can be sourced from public repositories including [GRSE](#), [ASC](#), [GLOBALGap](#), Best Aquaculture Practices ([BAP](#)), third party certification organisations, and other open-source data. Other sources of Tier 1 data include regional and national legislation (e.g. use of GMO raw materials in feeds, adherence to extended producer responsibility legislation), published LCA studies, protected area databases (e.g., European Environment Agency EU database on [Natura 2000](#)) and national statistics (e.g., FAO [FishStat](#)). Advantage of these Tier 1 data are that FAiR, i.e., findable, accessible, generally validated with different degrees of interoperability, and potentially re-usable. Weaknesses are that data are patchy (i.e., not available for all indicators) and generally at a high level, providing only a broad measure of indicator performance. Whilst all the above are public information, it might not be possible to automate data access and re-use, which suggests some level of additional processing for prospective Tier 1 entries for VeriFish. In contrast, Tier 2 data are provided by value chains, specifically relating to production methods, products and processes. The advantage of these data is relatively high degrees of granularity can across the different indicators, which can be used to assess performance. The disadvantages, however, are that this information is not readily findable or accessible, subject to bias or error, less interoperable, and potentially not re-useable.

3.11 Sources of data: Nutrients

Scientifically validated – largely Tier 1 – sources for nutrition indicators specific include:

1. Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO)

FAO/INFOODS Global Food Composition Database for Fish and Shellfish (uFiSh) provides nutrient information for fish, crustaceans, and molluscs including minerals, vitamins, amino acids, fatty acids, and proximates.

The FAO/INFOODS uFiSh database aligns well with FAIR principles, offering globally accessible and detailed nutrient information. However, improving interoperability with other databases through standardised formats could enhance usability across research domains.

2. World Health Organization (WHO)

Nutrition data portal encompasses several areas of nutrition and related indicators, including micronutrients, key indicators within the Global Nutrition Monitoring Framework, and nutrition-related health and development data.

The data portal is highly accessible and reusable, with a focus on health indicators. However, its integration with other global data platforms is limited, potentially reducing its interoperability for cross-sectoral analyses.

3. European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)

EFSA provides scientifically validated nutrition data, including indicators for assessing the safety and nutritional benefits of seafood in the European market such as the [EFSA Scientific Opinions](#).

EFSA's scientifically validated data is findable and reusable, and its strong focus on safety and nutrition aligns with FAIR principles, but broader accessibility and specificity might improve impact.

4. United States Department of Agriculture (USDA)

USDA's [FoodData Central](#) offers detailed nutrient profiles for various seafood products.

USDA FoodData Central exemplifies FAIR principles by offering detailed, openly accessible, and standardised data that can be integrated into research, but these data are less applicable for EU products.

5. Global Nutrition Report (GNR)

GNR includes data on the contribution of fish to global nutrition security, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, e.g., [Global Nutrition Reports](#).

The GNR provides accessible and reusable insights into the role of seafood in nutrition security. While data is highly relevant, enhanced findability through better indexing and metadata would FAIRness.

6. European Food Information Resource (EuroFIR)

EuroFIR [FoodExplorer](#) provided access to >40 national food composition databases, offering validated nutrient data for seafood and aquaculture products across Europe.

FoodExplorer is a robust example of a FAIR-compliant resource (albeit behind a pay-wall), and EuroFIR's the commitment to standardisation and harmonisation makes it a valuable tool for VeriFish.

7. National food composition databases

Most countries in Europe are running and maintaining a national food composition database with nutrient data about national consumed foods.

These databases are often findable and reusable within their respective countries. However, variability in data structure and standards limits their interoperability without further support from, for example, EuroFIR.

7. Seafood Nutrition Partnership (SNP)

SNP provides [research and data on the nutritional benefits of seafood](#), focusing on public health outcomes related to seafood consumption.

SNP's focus on public health outcomes enhances reusability of its research and data. However, improving findability and accessibility through centralised indexing would broaden its reach and impact.

8. Seafood Watch - Monterey Bay Aquarium

While primarily focused on sustainability, [Seafood Watch](#) provides insights into the nutritional value of different seafood species in relation to sustainable sourcing.

While not strictly a nutrient database, Seafood Watch provides valuable insights that could be FAIRer with more robust metadata and better integration with other nutritional and sustainability-focused platforms.

Overall, these sources provide critical data for advancing VeriFish goals, but increased adherence to FAIR principles, particularly in terms of interoperability and accessibility, would significantly enhance their utility.

4. Indicator Quality

Data quality is fundamental to the effectiveness of any indicators, particularly in areas such as sustainability, nutrition, and environment. High-quality data means indicators are accurate, reliable, and meaningful, providing a solid foundation for informed decision-making. In the context of aquafood, data quality is essential for assessing aspects such as resource use, social conditions, and nutritional values. Without robust, verifiable data, credibility of the VeriFish framework will be undermined, leading to misleading conclusions or ineffective actions. Therefore, ensuring data used are transparent, well-documented, and updated consistently (if not frequently) is crucial for development and use of VeriFish indicators that reflect the reality of aquafood production systems. High-quality data not only enhance trust amongst stakeholders but also support continuous improvement, enabling monitoring, evaluation, and adaptation of practices.

Criteria for assessing the quality of VeriFish's indicators include:

- 1. RELEVANCE:** Indicators must: (i) reflect key environmental impacts of aquaculture, such as resource use, pollution levels, biodiversity impacts, and carbon footprint; (ii) address labour conditions, community impacts, equity, and economic benefits across the aquafood supply chain; and (iii) accurately state nutrient values.
- 2. ACCURACY:** Data supporting the indicators must be scientifically validated, precise, and based on rigorous methodologies to ensure reliability across different contexts. Measurements must come from reputable sources and methodologies, like life cycle assessments (LCAs) or ecosystem studies, and data collected through established frameworks, such as fair trade certifications or verified surveys. Nutritional information must be derived from recognised food composition databases and/or peer-reviewed research.
- 3. TIMELINESS:** Indicators must be based on up-to-date data to reflect current trends and realities, including regularly updated measurements of resource use, emissions, and impacts, current labour data, market trends, and social impacts, particularly post-Covid-19 pandemic economic shifts, and EU-wide dietary guidelines.
- 4. TRANSPARENCY:** Sources and methodologies must be clearly defined and accessible, allowing stakeholders to verify the information behind each indicator. There must be (i) transparent reporting on how environmental data (e.g., carbon emissions, resource extraction) is collected and calculated; (ii) clear definitions of labour metrics, community engagement processes, and economic assessments; and (iii) documented sources for nutritional composition and health impacts.
- 5. COMPARABILITY:** Indicators must be standardised to allow comparisons across different contexts, regions, or time periods, allowing (i) comparisons of sustainability performance across species, production methods (e.g., aquaculture vs. wild catch), and regions; (ii) labour practices, economic benefits, and social impacts across different supply chains and communities; and (iii) consistent measures of nutrient content and health benefits to enable cross-comparisons between seafood products.

- 6. MEASURABILITY:** Data must be quantifiable, allowing for clear measurement and tracking of progress over time. Metrics such as CO₂ emissions, water use, or biodiversity loss must be easily measurable and scalable whilst employment rates, wages, community benefits, and economic outputs must be quantifiable. Nutrient concentrations and health outcomes must be measurable and based on standardised tests and analyses.
- 7. ACTIONABILITY:** Indicators must provide actionable insights for actors, enabling practical improvements or interventions. Insights must (i) inform actions to reduce emissions, enhance resource efficiency, or minimise biodiversity impacts; (ii) guide improvements in labour conditions, social equity, or economic resilience; and (iii) help improve public health outcomes by guiding better nutritional choices and ensuring food safety.
- 8. COST-EFFECTIVENESS:** Cost associated with collecting and maintaining data must be reasonable and not overly burdensome.
- 9. STAKEHOLDER INCLUSIVENESS:** Development and application of indicators must involve a wide range of actors and citizens, e.g., environmental scientists, regulators, and industry representatives, communities, labour representatives, supply chain stakeholders, NGOs, nutritionists, public health experts, and authorities.
- 10. ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS:** Indicators must respect ethical guidelines, ensuring no harm to the environment, communities, or citizens, i.e., Collection methods must not negatively impact ecosystems, promote fair labour practices and community well-being, and not compromise ethical or cultural values.

By applying these criteria, VeriFish can ensure that environmental, social and economic, and nutrition and health indicators are robust, trustworthy, and beneficial to stakeholders across the aquafood value chain. Moreover, criteria for assessing the quality of environmental, social, economic, and nutrition and health indicators can be directly linked to Task 2.2, which focuses on developing a scoring system and guidelines for communication based on the indicator framework. Specifically, these criteria will guide design and implementation of the scoring system, ensuring that the scoring is meaningful, reliable, and easy to understand for consumers and other stakeholders. Thus, data quality criteria—relevance, transparency, timeliness, etc.—will be used to develop guidelines on how to visualise and communicate VeriFish indicators. These guidelines will provide actors with a clear roadmap on how to effectively use the VeriFish scoring system, based on traffic light and distance-to-target systems, in communication campaigns, ensuring they can promote responsible consumption of aquafood products in an accessible and credible manner.

Later in the project quality criteria for data underlying the indicators will support development of a European Good Practice Recommendation (CWA) (WP4) for how to communicate on aquafood. For example, the indicators and communication guidelines must focus on the most pertinent aspects of aquafood sustainability, social responsibility, and nutrition. The CWA will emphasise the importance of selecting indicators that accurately reflect environmental, social, and nutritional concerns for European consumers. By grounding the CWA in these quality criteria, the European Good Practice Recommendation will ensure that aquafood communication is scientifically accurate, ethically sound, and accessible to all.

5. VeriFish Framework

The VeriFish Framework will be an innovative and comprehensive system designed to address the growing need for transparent and actionable sustainability metrics in the aquafood sector. By integrating three foundational pillars—Environmental, Social and Economic, and Nutrition and Health—it will provide a robust, multi-dimensional approach to assessing and communicating sustainability by diverse stakeholders, including producers, retailers, policymakers, to consumers. The framework will bridge gaps in data accessibility, communication, and decision-making, fostering a more sustainable consumption of aquafood in Europe.

The VeriFish Framework will be built on a tiered data system to accommodate diverse needs and capacities of aquafood actors. Tier 1 comprises publicly available data from global repositories. These datasets are highly accessible, generally free, and scientifically validated, offering broad yet less detailed sustainability insights. Tier 2 data, on the other hand, are specific to the value chain, encompassing production methods, practices, and proprietary details provided by producers. This dual-tier system will enable the framework to balance accessibility with granularity, ensuring that both high-level and detailed assessments can be made.

The framework will be underpinned by three pillars, each addressing critical dimensions of sustainability.

ENVIRONMENTAL PILLAR will focus on minimising ecological harm and promoting sustainable resource use within capture fisheries and aquaculture, leveraging scientifically validated indicators to measure and communicate key aspects, including stock status, climate and ecosystem impacts, and waste and pollution. This pillar will emphasise transparency, scientific rigour, and adaptability, allowing consumers to make informed decisions that protect aquatic ecosystems while maintaining productivity.

SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC PILLAR will guarantee that sustainability extends beyond environmental considerations, addressing the human and societal aspects of aquafood production. This pillar focuses on promoting fair labour practices, equitable economic benefits, and community well-being through labour conditions, community impacts, economic stability, and equity and access. This pillar will align with global sustainability goals, ensuring benefits of responsible aquafood production are shared across all sectors of society.

NUTRITION AND HEALTH PILLAR will highlight the critical role of aquafood in supporting human health and addressing dietary needs. This pillar will integrate data on nutritional composition of aquafood products with environmental and social and economic aspects, enabling actor to understand and communicate health benefits and consumers to make more informed decisions about consumption. Key areas of focus will include nutrient quality and dietary impact on health. This pillar will support development of guidelines emphasising the importance of aquafood in achieving balanced and sustainable diets.

The VeriFish framework will integrate these pillars into a cohesive system (including scoring and visualisation) that stakeholders can apply across various contexts. Producers and retailers can use the framework to demonstrate sustainability credentials, improve supply chain practices, and enhance consumer trust. Policymakers can leverage the indicators to develop regulations, incentives, and standards that promote

sustainable aquafood production. Consumers, empowered with transparent and verifiable information, can make informed purchasing decisions aligned with their values. The proposed flexibility allows the framework to accommodate emerging trends and challenges, such as the growing demand for sustainable aquafood, advancements in data technologies, and shifts in consumer preferences. By providing a structured approach to sustainability communication, VeriFish will ensure that aquafood chain actors can contribute to a more sustainable and equitable future.

Key features and innovations of the framework under development are:

SCIENTIFIC RIGOUR: framework is grounded in evidence-based methodologies, safeguarding the reliability and credibility of indicators.

TRANSPARENCY AND VERIFIABILITY: by sourcing data from publicly available repositories and value chain actors, VeriFish can ensure that claims are supported by verifiable information.

ACCESSIBILITY AND SCALABILITY: tiered data system accommodates diverse user needs, from high-level assessments to granular analyses.

HOLISTIC APPROACH: integration of environmental, social, economic, and health dimensions makes VeriFish a unique and comprehensive tool for sustainability assessment.

DIGITAL INTEGRATION: VeriFish will leverage digital platforms, such as its prototype web application, to enhance data sharing and stakeholder engagement.

The proposed VeriFish framework represents a critical step towards harmonising sustainability communication in the aquafood sector. However, its success depends on continuous refinement and stakeholder collaboration. Future developments might include expanding the framework to include additional indicators and data sources, enhancing interoperability with other sustainability frameworks and reporting systems, strengthening the role of digital tools, such as machine learning, to analyse and predict sustainability trends, and promoting global adoption through partnerships with other initiatives and organisations.

By addressing these challenges, VeriFish has the potential to become a global standard for sustainable aquafood practices, contributing to healthier ecosystems, communities, and diets.

6. Conclusions

The VeriFish project has developed a comprehensive set of indicators to assess and communicate sustainability in aquafood production and consumption. These indicators can – in the future – be applied in a framework based on three pillars—Environmental, Social and Economic, and Nutrition and Health—providing a systematic approach to measuring sustainability. The indicators draw from diverse data sources, structured into a dual-tier system, ensuring a balance between accessibility and specificity. This report underscores the role of robust indicators in simplifying sustainability communication and highlights their potential to address communication of the complexities of this sector effectively.

6.1. Summary of Findings

The indicators are designed to address sustainability challenges of capture fisheries and aquaculture whilst also incorporating human health and social dimensions. Key findings include:

ENVIRONMENTAL INDICATORS: Indicators such as stock status, carbon emissions, habitat impacts, and bycatch provide a robust measure of ecological sustainability. For example, metrics like B_{MSY} and F_{MSY} assess the health of fish stocks, while CO_2 equivalents and habitat impact scores address broader environmental concerns.

SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC INDICATORS: Although less mature than the environmental indicators, these metrics will focus on labour practices, community benefits, and economic viability. Indicators such as compliance with labour standards and equitable access to resources provide foundational insights but require further development and data integration.

NUTRITION AND HEALTH INDICATORS: These indicators focus on the nutritional value of aquafoods, emphasising high-quality protein, omega-3 fatty acids, and micronutrients. They are underpinned by measurable attributes such as macronutrient content and bioavailability, with links to public health.

The dual-tier system ensures that indicators are both practical and adaptable, with Tier 1 offering high-level insights from publicly available data and Tier 2 providing granular, value chain-specific details.

6.2. Implications for Future Work

The findings from this report have implications for design of the VeriFish framework and application of sustainability indicators, especially D2.2 Indicator Framework developed (M12, FORTH). Accuracy and validity of indicators depend heavily on data quality. Enhancing data collection and standardisation efforts will improve reliability across all pillars. The relatively nascent state of social and economic indicators calls for

targeted research and collaboration with experts to refine metrics that reflect social equity, fair labour practices, and economic resilience. Linking environmental, social, and nutritional indicators more explicitly could offer a holistic view of sustainability, aligning with broader policy goals and consumer expectations. Finally, the indicators must be actively integrated into regulatory systems, certification schemes, and industry practices to achieve tangible sustainability outcomes.

6.3. Recommendations for stakeholders

The indicators and the broader VeriFish framework offer actionable insights that stakeholders across the aquafood sector can utilise to drive meaningful progress. For the industry, environmental indicators such as CO₂ emissions and stock status serve as essential tools for guiding sustainable fishing and aquaculture practices. Similarly, implementing social indicators can help demonstrate a commitment to equitable labour practices and community well-being. Policymakers can benefit from incorporating these indicators into sustainability certifications and regulatory standards, thereby harmonising assessment methods across regions and sectors. Prioritising funding for robust data collection systems, particularly in the social and economic domains, would further enhance the reliability and applicability of these metrics.

For researchers, the primary focus should be on the continued validation and refinement of indicators, especially in underdeveloped areas like socio-economic impacts and nutrition-related sustainability metrics. Additionally, exploring methodologies to integrate cross-pillar indicators will provide a more holistic view of sustainability. In the longer term, consumers and NGOs are encouraged to advocate for greater transparency in the adoption and application of these indicators by producers and policymakers. The indicator framework is also instrumental in guiding consumers towards more sustainable and health-conscious purchasing decisions.

By emphasising scientifically validated and verifiable metrics, the VeriFish framework establishes a prototype tool for aligning industry practices with global sustainability goals while supporting informed decision-making.